

CONDENSATIONS OF ARYL DIAZONIUM SALTS WITH REACTIVE UNSATURATED COMPOUNDS. PART III. ACTION OF ARYL DIAZONIUM CHLORIDES WITH ACRYLIC ACID

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The condensations afford a more practical way for the synthesis of cinnamic acids than the Koelsch's method.

In Part II of this paper (*this issue*, p.383), the condensations of aryl diazonium chlorides having a negative substituent were effected with maleic acid in the presence of copper chloride and sodium acetate, resulting in the formation of cinnamic acids, thus :

and contrary to expectation, the use of acetone was found unnecessary and harmful. The cinnamic acids could be easily obtained in a sufficient state of purity from the reaction mixture as to merit the reaction fit for preparatory purpose. Earlier, Koelsch (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1943, 65, 57) had reacted four aryl diazonium chlorides with methyl acrylate and acrylonitrile and from the methyl α -chlorohydrocinnamates and α -chlorohydrocinnamionitriles so formed :

obtained the cinnamic acids after their dehalogenation and hydrolysis. In the present investigation aryl diazonium chlorides have been condensed with acrylic acid to ascertain how far the reactions compare with Koelsch's method for obtaining cinnamic acids.

When the various aryl diazonium chlorides are reacted (*vide experimental*) with acrylic acid in the presence of copper chloride and sodium acetate, but in the absence of acetone, condensations occur to afford the cinnamic acids directly, thus

(I)

with only traces of the α -halogenated hydrocinnamic acids which give (I) even during extraction of the reaction products with warm aqueous sodium bicarbonate. The condensations have been effected in larger dilution than those with maleic acids and the yields of cinnamic acids by the two methods compare admirably.

The yields of the cinnamic acids indicate that acrylic acid can adequately replace the use of its methyl ester or the nitrile. The preparation of *p*-nitrocinnamic acid by the present method is definitely superior to that of the Koelsch's procedure. The acid is obtained in larger yield than the nitrile in the latter method and the task of handling a black tarry reaction product

is obviated. In other cases, although Koelsch's method gives relatively a large yield of the condensation products, the loss sustained in obtaining the free cinnamic acids after their hydrolysis would counterbalance this advantage. Moreover, the omission of acetone as solvent, and the direct use of only aqueous acrylic acid are the added advantages.

It may be recalled that when of *p*-nitrobenzene diazonium chloride is reacted with crotonic acid (Koelsch and Boekelheide, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1944, 66, 414), the reaction mixture yields only a tarry mass from which the acid of m.p. 167-68° (cf. also Meerwein *et al.*, *J. prakt. Chem.*, 1939, *ii*, 152, 261) could be obtained after esterification of the tarry mass and its subsequent hydrolysis. It is now found that even when the use of acetone is omitted in this reaction, aqueous sodium bicarbonate, as is done in experiments with acrylic acid, is able to extract out only a tarry acid from the reaction product.

EXPERIMENTAL

The amines were of the quality mentioned in a previous investigation (*loc. cit.*)

The acrylic acid was obtained in a batch preparation by boiling for 2 to 3 hours β -chloropropionic acid (25 g.) with 2*N* aqueous sodium hydroxide (500 c.c.). The alkaline liquor was acidified with dilute sulphuric acid (1 : 5, 125 c.c.) and then distilled till about 400 c.c. were collected as the distillate. An aliquot of 80 c.c. of the distillate contained 1.8 g. of acrylic acid (*M/40*) as determined alkalimetrically, and this much solution was used in each experiment with acrylic acid.

Condensations of various Aryl Diazonium Chlorides with Acrylic Acid in the presence of Sodium Acetate and Copper Chloride

The amines (0.025 *M*) in hydrochloric acid (conc., 6 c.c.) and water (9-12 c.c.) were diazotised with sodium nitrite (2.5 g., 68% pure) in water (7 c.c.) as in the previous investigation. In a separate beaker were taken aqueous solution of acrylic acid (80 c.c., *vide supra*), sodium acetate (5.75 g.) and copper chloride (1 g.). Each diazotised amine was condensed with such a mixture. The total bulk of the solution was about 100 c.c. Reactions were vigorous with the nitro- and halogen-substituted diazonium chlorides. Reaction mixtures with the *o*-nitro-, and the 2 : 6-dichlorobenzene diazonium chlorides (*vide infra*) contained more tarry matter. In every case the insoluble residue was filtered off from the reaction mixture and extracted with 5% aqueous sodium bicarbonate. This treatment also eliminated whatever little halogen acid was there in the crude product. The acids, obtained on acidification with dilute sulphuric acid, were found to be unsaturated, and after purification were found to possess melting points which were not depressed when they were mixed with a corresponding aryl acrylic acid, prepared by the maleic acid method. The results are recorded in the following table.

No acid could be obtained from diazotised aniline, *o*-xylydine, *o*- and *p*-anisidines and *p*-aminoacetanilide.

TABLE I
 β Aryl acrylic acid

Amine (diazotised).	Wt.	Amount.	Yield.	M.p.	Equivalent		*Yield of the pure nitrile.
					Found.	Calc.	
<i>p</i> -Nitroaniline	(3.45 g.)	2.9 g.	60.1%	285-86°	194	193	48%
<i>p</i> -Chloroaniline	(3.20 g.)	1.3	28.5	238-40°	186	182.5	—
<i>p</i> -Bromoaniline	(4.30g.)	1.5	26.5	249-51°	232	227	—
<i>m</i> -Nitroaniline	(3.45g.)	1.4	29.0	196-86°	195	193	38%
<i>m</i> -Chloroaniline	(3.20g.)	1.3	28.0	174-75°	186	182.5	—
<i>m</i> -Bromoaniline	(4.30g.)	1.5	26.5	175-77°	234	227	—
<i>o</i> -Nitroaniline	(3.45g.)	0.8	7.3	238-39°	197	193	—
<i>o</i> -Chloroaniline	(3.20g.)	1.2	28.0	199-99°	188	182.5	—
<i>o</i> -Bromoaniline	(4.30g.)	1.4	26.2	210-12°	230	227	—
<i>o</i> -Iodoaniline	(2.70g., <i>M/80</i>)	0.9	25.6	212-14°	—	—	—
4-Methyl-3-nitroaniline	(3.80g.)	0.8	15.4	170-72°	212	207	—
2:6-Dichloroaniline	(3.60g.)	1.1	19.8	181-83°	220	217	—
α -Naphthylamine	(3.60g.)	0.8	7.0	205-08°	—	—	—
β -Naphthylamine	(3.60g.)	0.5	10.0	193-95°	201	198	—

*Koelech's method.

The experiment of the reaction of *p*-nitrobenzene diazonium chloride with crotonic acid (prepared from paraldehyde, malonic acid and glacial acetic acid) was also repeated. The reaction product on extraction with sodium bicarbonate yielded only a tarry mass. The latter was obtained more in amount in the absence of acetone than in its presence. The tarry acid mass polymerised to an amorphous solid on keeping.

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